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PREMATURE BIRTH AND STRESS

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Summary. Moskalenko T. I., Cherniyevska S. G., Bichevska R. G., Bykova N. A. **PREMATURE BIRTH AND STRESS.** - *The Odessa National Medical University, Ukraine; e-mail: rozaliibichevska@gmail.com*. The level of postnatal depression indicators in accordance with the Edinburgh scale in pregnant and postpartum women was studied and analyzed. Our study has proven an increase in the level of premature births and the premature babies, and operative deliveries in the group with a high level of postpartum depression. It was recommended to manage high-risk pregnancies using psychological counseling to prevent possible complications. **The aim** - to study and analyze the level of postpartum depression in pregnant women using the Edinburgh Scale. **Materials and methods.** 75 pregnant women aged 17 – 47 y. o. have been under examination. In the groups under observation the questionnaires were analyzed. The level of stress at the beginning of pregnancy and at childbirth, characteristics of their course, the condition of newborns have been established. The standard Statistica information processing systems were used. The women under examination were divided into 3 groups according to the stress level: with no stress, with moderate compensated stress and with symptoms of severe stress. **Results.** Analysis of the obtained indicators in the studied groups of pregnant women found that with increasing stress levels, there was an increase in premature births, placental dysfunction, operative deliveries, and the use of EDA. Analysis of age-related indicators showed that in patients with high rates of postpartum depression, childbirth ended prematurely, and this indicator did not depend on the age of the women. When analyzing indicators by category of child maturity, it was found that extremely premature children were born to women with high levels of postpartum depression.

Key words: premature birth, premature babies, EPDS - Edinburgh Postnatal Depression (Scale)

Реферат. Москаленко Т. Я., Чернієвська С. Г., Бічевська Р. Г., Бикова Н. А. **ПЕРЕДЧАСНІ ПОЛОГІ ТА СТРЕСС.** Вивчено та проаналізовано рівень показників післяпологової депресії за Едінбургською шкалою у вагітних та жінок в післяпологовому періоді. В дослідженні доведено збільшення рівня передчасних пологів, народження вкрай недоношених малюків, оперативних розроджень в групі жінок з високим рівнем післяродової депресії. Запропановано ведення вагітних із підвищеним рівнем стресу з залученням психоемоційної підтримки та психологічного консультування з метою профілактики можливих ускладнень.

Ключові слова: передчасні пологи, Едінбургська шкала післяпологової депресії, недоношені немовлята.

Russian military aggression against our state contributed to the growth of negative factors on the mental state of our population [1, 5]. Studies of the impact of war on Ukrainian society report an increase in symptoms of stress disorder [3]. Pregnant women in the realities of war often find themselves in state of depression and psychosis [6]. Due to extremely severe prolonged stress in pregnant women, childbirth is increasingly completed before term, the number of urgent surgical interventions, premature births, and the birth rate of extremely premature babies is increasing [2, 6]. Immature children are particularly vulnerable and require special care for their survival, and raising such children is very expensive for the state [3, 6]. The high economic component of caring for such babies consists of intensive therapy, providing medical, rehabilitation, and educational needs. The social component is also very important because parents are faced with the death of a premature baby or spend a long time in wards with sick children [6].

Psychological state provokes metabolic and functional changes in the body, which can affect the condition of the fetus. Vegetative changes affect the diet, lifestyle of pregnant women, which disrupts the availability of oxygen and glucose to the fetus, endocrine functions of the placenta deteriorate, which stimulates oxidative stress of carrying, and high levels of cortisol stimulate uterine activity [6].

The problem of premature birth has always been particularly relevant in the context of modern research in field of Obstetrics and perinatology. Understanding the symbiotic nature of such complex phenomena as humans, modern perinatology must investigate the problem of premature birth, considering the achievements of other sciences in general and psychology in particular [8].

The frequency of premature birth in the world ranges from 8-12% depending on level of development of the country [6,7]. There are many reasons for premature birth, both physiological and psychological. Each case is individual: previous experience, external environment, emotional trauma, losses, and many other factors. All of them can affect the health and condition of the pregnant woman, and accordingly the child [1, 6]. Premature birth is the second leading cause of death in children under 5 years of age. According to international organizations, complications after premature birth account for 35% of the 3,1 million annual neonatal deaths worldwide. Premature birth increases the risk of death from pneumonia and acquired infection and can cause the child to have a lag in physical and mental development, cerebral palsy, epilepsy, and problems with vision, hearing, and breathing [7, 8]. Today Ukrainian doctors manage to care for up to 90% of extremely premature babies, and most of these children do not lag their peers born on time [2]. Preserving every newborn life and promoting its full development is a top priority for Ukraine today and in the coming decades to preserve the human potential of our country [1, 3].

Purpose: The investigate the impact of prenatal stress on the features of the features of the psycho-emotional state of the pregnant woman, the course of pregnancy and childbirth in conditions of military aggression. Choose appropriate tactics for managing patients in accordance and intercity standards for providing. Focusing on the goal, we paid attention to the socio-psychological situation in which pregnant women who gave birth prematurely found themselves.

Materials and methods: To achieve the goal, testing of prenatal and postpartum depressive state of pregnant women was carried out using the Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale (EPDS) [7, 8]. The EPDS is a mental health assessment tool that aims to identify women who may need help and support. A questionnaire-based technique designed to identify depressive states during pregnancy. The scale was developed in 1987 by Edinburgh and Livingston. The technique is simple, easy to use, and can be completed by patients themselves. It is proposed for the examination of individuals with a high depressive state to quickly eliminate negative psycho-emotional [8]. This psychodiagnostics technique was recommended in Ukraine since the beginning of the war. It is recommended that all women undergo EPDS at least once, but preferably twice: during pregnancy and after childbirth. Considering that according to WHO, 1 in 10 men experience symptoms of postpartum depression, the scale also recommended for them to fill out the EPDS can be used not only for pregnant women, women in labor, and members of the newborn family. The questionnaire consists of 10 items, each of has 4 answer options with a gradation of 4 degrees of severity. The scale examines such psychological states as anxiety inability to laugh, panic fear, tearfulness, guilt, difficulty falling asleep, sadness, suicidal thoughts, worry, and coping deficit. The analysis indicators are taken for each scale separately and the total number of

points scored [8].

0-4 points- low level of postpartum depression

5-11 points – average level of postpartum depression

12 or more points–high level of postpartum depression

The study selected 75 pregnant women aged 17 to 47 who were registered for pregnancy at an antenatal clinic and birth in the municipal profit maternity hospital №10 Odessa city council. The study was conducted in 2022-2023 from January to December inclusive. In the studied groups, the results of the questionnaire were analyzed to determine the level of stress at the beginning of pregnancy and childbirth, considering the characteristics of their course, the condition of newborns, and considering average statistical indicators using standard Statistical information processing systems. They were divided into 3 groups according to their stress level: with no stress, with moderate compensated stress and with symptoms of severe stress.

Research results and their discussion

In the study, we obtained the results of indicators of the psych emotional state of women in labor in dynamics, indicators of the course of pregnancy by the level of depression. We conducted an analysis of indicators of the level of postpartum depression by the age of the women and the degree of the woman and the degree of prematurity and gestational age.

Table 1

Analysis of indicators of the level of postpartum depression by age

Level of depression	Total number	17-23 years old	24-35 years old	36-47 years old
Low level of depression.	9	2 (23%)	4 (44%)	3(33%)
Intermediate level of depress.	14	4 (28,6%)	5 (35,7%)	5 (35,7%)
High level of depression	52	12 (23%)	20 (38,5%)	20 (38,5%)
Total number	75	18	29	28

The high rate of postpartum depression in women aged 17 to 23 was 23% in the of 24-35 in 38,5% of respondents and 38,5% over 36 years. The average level of depression in the group aged 17 to 23 was 28,6% of the respondent of the second group and the third group it was observed in 35,5%. The low level of depression in the age group of 17 was 23%, in the group of women aged 24 to 35 it was 44%, and in the age group of 36-47 it was 33%. Therefore, the high risk of developing depression regardless of age is almost more than half of surveyed women.

Diagram 1

When analyzing the results high anxiety rates were found in 54(75%) women, most often in the age group of 24-35(44,2%). Feelings of panic without good reason-34(45,3%) were more common in women also in the age group of 24-35 (42,2%). Feelings of guilt 29 (38,7%) were observed in all groups of patients regardless of age. Insomnia was found in 25 (33,4%) women aged 35 years and older. Tearfulness was characteristic of 23(30,7%) women aged 35 years and older. Feeling of unhappiness in 9 (39,1%) cases and in most cases were in those surveyed aged 36 years and older. Suicidal thoughts were experienced by 1 woman aged 19 who had a family tragedy.

Diagram 2

Thus, the threat of premature birth was diagnosed in 10% of women in the first group, 25% of the second and 65% of the third group. Placental dysfunction was noted in 9% of the first group, 28% of the second and 63% of the third group. The frequency of caesarean section increased in women with a higher level of stress in 11% of women in the first group, 30% of women in group 2 and 59% of the third group. When analyzing the indicators by the category of child maturity premature we saw that extremely premature babies were born to women with a high level of postpartum depression. Analysis of the obtained indicators in the studied groups of pregnant women found that with increasing stress levels, there was an increase in the threat of premature birth, placental dysfunction, surgical interventions, and the use of epidural anesthesia.

It was analyzed that 15% were in the first group. 35% in the second and 50% respectively. The frequency of use of painkillers also increased, used by 25% of women in the first group, 30% of women in the second and 45% of the third group.

Thus, when analyzing the stress levels that provoke premature birth and the birth of immature babies, we see that high levels of depression are in first place.

Analysis of indicators of the level of postpartum depression by gestational age

	Total number	Low level of depression.	Intermediate level of depression	High level of depression
Extremely premature babies from 22 to 27 weeks up to 1000 g	5	0	1 (20%)	4 (80%)
Very premature babies from 28 до 31 weeks.(weight less than 1500 g)	14	1 (7,2%)	3 (21,4%)	10 (71,4%)
Moderately premature babies from 32 to 37 weeks (weight 1500 less than 2500 g)	88	4 (4,5%)	10 (11,3%)	74 (84,2%)
Total number	107	5	14	88

Thus, when analyzing the stress levels that provoke premature birth and the birth of immature babies, we see that high levels of depression are in first place.

When analyzing indicators by category of child maturity, we saw that extremely premature babies were born to women with high levels of postpartum depression, and indicators such as anxiety, panic, worry, insomnia, and feelings of guilt were too high. Moderately premature babies were born to women who were characterized by high levels of guilt, unhappiness, and anxiety.

Conclusions:

1. Under military conditions, pregnancy is accompanied by depressive psycho emotional states, which provokes the risk of premature birth and the birth of extremely premature babies.

2. The Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale makes it possible to quickly identify psych emotional disorders in the prenatal and postpartum periods and provide timely qualified support according to the assessment of condition.

3. Involving psychological counseling in the management of pregnant women with elevated stress levels is necessary to prevent complication.

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